

ISic0307

Funerary altar for Quintus Atilius Severus, duumvir of Catania

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

2017.03.21

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 230

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 135 cm

Width 89 cm

Depth 85 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-7: 35-44 mm

Interlineation

Not measured: mm

Text

1. D (is) · M (anibus) · s (acrum) ·
2. Q (uinto) · Atilio · Q (uinti) · f (ilio) · Cla (udia) · Severo
4. praef (ecto) · fabr (um) ·
5. Iivir (o) · suf (fragiis) ·
6. popul (i) · cre
7. ato

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Sacred to the shades of the underworld. (Set up for) Quintus Atilius Severus, son of Quintus, of the

Claudian tribe, praefectus fabrum, appointed duumvir by the votes of the people

Translation (it)

Commentary

The inscription attests to a member of the elite of the Roman colony of Catania. Quintus Atilius is presumably a member of the equestrian order, having held the military office in the imperial legions of praefectus fabrum (literally "prefect of the craftsmen/engineers": the precise role of the post is not entirely clear). Atilius also held the chief magistracy of the colonia, the duumvirate (a pair of annually appointed magistrates). The record of appointment by vote of the people is unusual: explicit statements to this effect are rare, with the result that, although in theory all such appointments were by popular vote, many historians (e.g. Mommsen and Liebenam) have concluded that under the empire it was more common for the appointments effectively to be made by co-optation by the decuriones (town councillors), and a formal popular vote therefore constituted an honour, whence the choice to record it explicitly as here. Both the Claudia and the Quirina tribes (formal divisions of Roman citizens) are attested at Catania.

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